

ARTEMIS

ARTEMIS User Needs Survey

Curator / Archivist

Digital Tools, Monitoring Practices, and Data Acquisition

Digital Tools or Technologies

Digital Tools or Technologies used to Monitor Condition

Data collected in Real Time

Challenges in Monitoring Conditions

Curator / Archivist

Data Types, Formats, and Interoperability Standards

Types of Data

Data Format

Standard or Protocols

Curator / Archivist

Data Accessibility, Sharing Practices, and Collaboration Platforms

Data Structure and Accessibility

Use of Collaborative Digital Platforms

Main Difficulties in Sharing Data

ARTEMIS

Curator / Archivist
3D Modelling, Digital Simulations, and Integration of Digital Technologies

Curator / Archivist
Digital Twin Applications, Functional Expectations, and Future Adoption

